

Chemical fractionation and distribution of metals in contaminated urban soil in Zhuzhou City, South Central China

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Abstract : The present study was conducted to determine the chemical fractions of heavy metals, to assess the current and potential environmental risks and to evaluate the mobility and bioavailability of metals in contaminated urban soils. Sequential extraction procedure was applied to fractionate the metal content into exchangeable fraction, carbonate fraction, fraction bound to Fe-Mn oxides, fraction bound to organic matter and residual fraction. Chemical speciation (Tessier, 1979) study revealed that Cd in soil prevails mostly in exchangeable fractions (26.383%). The overall percentage of metal content in different sequential fractions is in the sequence of Residual > Organic > Fe-Mn Oxides > Carbonate ≈ Exchangeable and the order of metals in each fractions are as follows – Exchangeable : Cd > Cu > Pb > As, Carbonate : Cd > Pb > Cu > As, Fe-Mn Oxides : Pb > Cd > Cu > As, Organic : As > Cu > Pb > Cd and Residual : As > Pb > Cu > Cd. Elemental concentrations from each sequential extraction step were measured using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, IRIS Intrepid II XSP, USA). The pH value of the soils in the study area ranged from 6.44 to 7.05 (mean 6.67), indicating an acidic to neutral type of surface soils. The eco-toxicological assessment of the studied soil using the mobility factor indices revealed the following sequence : Cd (40.627) > Pb (14.941) ≥ Cu (14.399) > As (5.377). Mobility factor indices for soil metals revealed a high environmental contamination risk for Cd, which indicates a serious environmental threat.

Keywords : Heavy metals, soil, speciation, mobility, sequential extractions, ICP-OES.

Introduction

Metal concentration in the soils of urban areas cannot be attributed solely to geological factors alone whereas the anthropogenic inputs also play a predominant role in the development and modification of the soil. Soil can be considered as a sink and source of pollution with the capacity to transfer pollutants to the groundwater, into the food chain and into the human body^{1,2}. Mining and metal smelting activities have been known to be the main sources of hazardous heavy metals^{3,4}. The soils surrounding metal mining and smelting sites have been exposed to high contamination with trace elements³ which ultimately damage the surrounding ecosystem. Smelting of non-ferrous metals and burning of fossil fuels are one of the major sources of arsenic pollution⁵. Environmental concerns in such metal smelting areas are primarily related to the physico-chemical and biological disturbances of the surrounding landscape.

The determination of total concentration of metals in soil is generally not sufficient to assess the environmental impact and thus an estimation of the bioavailable fraction is necessary. So the sequential extraction therefore, permits to precisely identify the origins of the metals and to better understand their geochemical cycles and mobility. The sequential fraction distribution pattern is related to metal properties, soil compositions and properties⁶⁻⁸ and metal fractions could directly influence their transfer and bioavailability in soils. The speciation of metals, is taken into account the fractionation of the total metal content into exchangeable (F1 : bound to exchangeable sites of clay minerals), carbonates (F2 : acid extractable), reducible (F3 : bound to Fe/Mn oxides), oxidisable (F4 : bound to organic matter/sulfides) and residual (F5 : bound to clay minerals) forms. The metals in the exchangeable and carbonates phases are easy to transfer and transform, so the metals in these phases are easy to be released from

soil and cause series of biohazards. The metals in reducible and oxidisable phases are more stable than in F1 and F2, though there are also possibilities for them to be released when the environmental conditions change. The fraction in the residual phase contains metals that are bound to the mineral matrix and hard to be released from the soil. Thus, heavy metals accumulate in soils in various chemical forms, i.e. exchangeable, carbonate-associated, Fe-Mn oxide-associated, organic-associated and residual forms. So it is important to assess the bio-availability and mobility of heavy metals and to understand chemical behavior and fate of heavy metal contaminants in soils⁹. The mobility, bioavailability and potential toxicity of metal in the soil depend on various factors like (1) the concentration of metals in soil solution, (2) the nature of its association with other soluble species and (3) the ability of soil to release the metal from the solid phase. The objectives of this study were : (i) to investigate the distribution and concentrations of metals and metalloid in contaminated soil; (ii) to determine the chemical fractions of metals, to assess the current and potential risk to the studied area and (iii) to evaluate the mobility and bioavailability of metals.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

In order to obtain the specific objective of the study, soil samples ($n = 7$) were collected from the contaminated sites of urban area near metal mining-smelting activities, analysed to determine the chemical fractions of metals (Cd, Pb and Cu) and metalloid (As) with the application of sequential extraction procedure. The collected soil samples were put in polyethylene bags and immediately sent to the laboratory for further analysis. The samples were air-dried, ground, passed through a 2-mm sieve, and homogenized. All glass- and plastic-ware was soaked in 5% (v/v) nitric acid overnight and rinsed thoroughly with deionized water before use. The pH was measured in the soil extracts (1 : 2.5 solid/distilled water [w/v]) using a glass electrode pH meter. The collected soils have been subjected to two types of digestion procedures; a sequential extraction procedure (SEP) and a total acid digestion. Tessier method (1979)¹⁰ was applied to fractionate the metal content from three soil samples (S1, S2 and S3) into exchangeable fraction, carbonate fractions, fraction bound to Fe-Mn oxides, fraction bound to organic matter and

residual fraction. Elemental concentrations from each sequential extraction step were measured using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometer (ICP-OES, IRIS Intrepid II XSP, USA).

Analytical precision and quality control :

Care has been taken for sample collection and preservation during every experimental procedure. Glassware was properly cleaned and reagents were of analytical grade. Quality assurance of metal analysis was assessed using duplicates, standard reference materials for soil obtained from China National Center for Standard Reference Materials (SRM; Soil : GBW-08303) and standard reference solution in the process of analysis in order to verify the accuracy and precision of the digestion procedure and subsequent analysis. The recovery for the analyzed heavy metals in the standard material was around 95–104%. For metal analysis, standard reference solution (1000 mg/L) was used for calibration and standardization of instrument. Intermediate solutions were prepared carefully by diluting stock standard solution with freshly prepared distilled water.

Internal check recovery of metals :

In order to obtain the accuracy of the results, the sum of metal concentrations in each chemical phase of the soil samples were compared with the total digestion concentration values. The recovery of the extraction procedure was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Recovery (\%)} = \frac{[F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4 + \text{Residual fraction}]}{[\text{Total digestion}]} \times 100$$

where F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , F_4 and RF refer to the concentration extracted in each fraction and the total concentration of heavy metals, respectively. A separate digestion of the soil sample was performed to determine the total metal contents by digestion with mixture of HF-HNO₃-HClO₄. The differences between the total content of soil and the sum of the individual phase (F_1 , F_2 , F_3 , F_4 and RF) concentrations were not greater than 11% indicating good agreement between the total concentration and the sum of sequential extraction results.

Results and discussion

Distribution of heavy metals in surface soil :

Distribution of total concentration of heavy metals in surface soil is represented in Table 1. The limit values for

Table 1. pH and the total concentrations of Pb, Cd, Cu and As in soils^a

Sample	pH	Pb	Cd	Cu	As
S1	6.445	947	32.274	132	72.636
S2	6.526	914	30.471	130	67.398
S3	6.786	873	31.292	128	72.853
S4	7.053	824	27.654	124	65.325
S5	6.587	937	30.638	127	70.786
S6	6.849	927	29.654	130	70.672
S7	6.458	912	31.457	134	68.974
Min	6.445	824	27.654	124	65.325
Max	7.053	947	32.274	134	72.853
Average	6.672	904.86	30.491	129.29	69.806
SD	0.229	42.79	1.501	3.302	2.756
Limit value		500	1.0	400	40.0

^aAll values are in mg/kg except pH.

metals set by the State Environmental Protection Administration of China (SEPAC, 1995)¹¹ in soils are also represented in Table 1. The heavy metals viz. Pb, Cd, Cu and As in the studied soils are in the range of 824–947 mg/kg, 27.654–32.274 mg/kg, 124–134 mg/kg and 65.325–72.853 mg/kg, with an overall mean \pm SD of 904.86 \pm 42.79 mg/kg, 30.491 \pm 1.501 mg/kg, 129.29 \pm 3.302 mg/kg and 69.806 \pm 2.756 mg/kg respectively. The total metal concentrations in the soils demonstrated different distribution patterns at the various stations. The highest Pb and Cd concentration was observed at the sampling site S1 where pH exhibited lower value, which influences metal mobility. The determination of total metal content is important because it determines the size of the metal pool in the soils and thus the potential for metal uptake by plants, though the entire metal content is not in bioavailable form. The mean values of metal concentrations can be arranged in the order Pb > Cu > As > Cd. Comparing the results of heavy metal contents with standards range (GB 15618-1995), data showed that the concentrations of Cu in this area are lower than standard (Cu : 400 mg/kg). However concentrations of Cd, Pb and As in this study are higher than standard range (Cd : 1.0 mg/kg, Pb : 500 mg/kg and As : 40 mg/kg). The analytical results indicated that the total concentrations of metals (Cd and Pb) and metalloid (As) were elevated in surface soils for all samples.

Soil pH generally plays an important role in metal bioavailability, toxicity and leaching capability to the sur-

rounding environment. The pH value of the surface soils in the study area ranged from 6.445 to 7.053 with an overall mean \pm SD of 6.672 \pm 0.229, indicating an acidic to neutral type of surface soil. Acid soils (pH < 6.5) account for about 28.57% of the soil, neutral soils (pH of 6.5–7.5) account for 71.43% and no alkaline soils (pH > 7.5) was observed in the experimental soil samples.

Correlation study :

The mobilization and distribution of metals in soil/sediment systems are dependent on various physical, chemical and biological factors and processes. pH is the most important physico-chemical factors controlling metal mobilization. Correlation analysis was done between pH and various heavy metals in the soil samples to assess the leaching possibility and the results are presented in Table 2. There was no positive correlation observed in the Cd ($r = -0.852$), Pb ($r = -0.776$) and Cu ($r = -0.786$) concentrations with the pH of the studied soils. Comparatively lower pH was observed at S1 and facili-

Table 2. Pearson correlations among different metals in surface soils

	pH	Pb	Cd	Cu	As
pH	1				
Pb	-0.776	1			
Cd	-0.852	0.705	1		
Cu	-0.786	0.667	0.753	1	
As	-0.370	0.576	0.760	0.370	1

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

tates the leaching of metals in the soil. Mobility of arsenic in surface soils is dependent on various parameters, among which adsorption of arsenate onto soil particles is very important. The mobility of arsenate (As^{5+}) and arsenite (As^{3+}) is a function of their adsorption, which in turn is controlled primarily by pH^{12,13}. In present study, the concentration of As in soils was negatively correlated with pH ($r = -0.370$). This result is in agreement with the results of other study¹⁴ where the concentration of As in soils was also negatively correlated with pH ($r = -0.370$). Positive correlations was observed between the heavy metals like Cd and Pb ($r = 0.705$), Cd and Cu ($r = 0.753$), Pb and As ($r = 0.576$), As and Cd ($r = 0.760$) could indicate the same or similar source input likely resulting from metal mining-smelting activities.

Table 3. Order of metals in each fraction of sequential extraction

Fraction	Order of metals
Exchangeable	Cd > Cu > Pb > As
Carbonate	Cd > Pb > Cu > As
Fe-Mn Oxides	Pb > Cd > Cu > As
Organic	As > Cu > Pb > Cd
Residual	As > Pb > Cu > Cd

Speciation of metals and their retention in surface soils :

Speciation/partitioning study helps to determine the binding character and chemical forms of metals, extent of retention and mobility/mobilization in surface soil. The solid phase chemical speciation and quantification of different species of heavy metals is very important tool to assess the soil quality. Metals accumulations in solid phases are known to occur in major forms; exchangeable fraction, carbonate fraction, reducible (oxides of Fe and Mn), oxidisable (organic matter and sulfide bound) and residual (lithogenic fractions strongly bounded). These categories have different characteristics with respect to remobilization under changing environmental condition. The sequential extraction procedure (SEP) applied in this study is composed of five steps. Metal association with the different sequential fractions observed in this study were expressed as average percentage and represented in Fig. 1. The association of cadmium with the different sequential fractions was observed in this study as follows : I – Exchangeable species (26.383%), II – Carbonates (14.244%), III – Fe-Mn oxides (19.901%), IV – Organic fraction (9.271%) and V – Residual fractions (30.201%). From the results as shown in Fig. 1, about 70% of the total Cd in the soils

is associated with the non-residual fractions. So, bivalent cadmium appeared in almost adequate amounts within all fractions except in organic fraction. Cd is mobilized during first sequential extraction stage that may affect biological organisms. Cadmium (Cd) is obviously higher in abundance among the four elements in the exchangeable fraction. The abundance of Cd in the exchangeable fraction was 26.383%. The high proportion of the chemically reactive forms of Cd implies a high ecological risk¹⁵.

The association of lead with the different sequential fractions was observed as follows : I – Exchangeable species (4.385%), II – Carbonates (10.556%), III – Fe-Mn oxides (28.756%), IV – Organic fraction (16.340%) and V – Residual fractions (39.963%). From the results as shown in Fig. 1, about 60% of the total Pb in the soils is associated with the non-residual fractions. Besides metal smelting activities, a considerable proportion of Pb in the environment is of anthropogenic origin, because it is an important additive that has been widely used in many chemical products. A major portion of Pb is bound to the Fe/Mn oxides with comparable amounts associated with the exchangeable fraction, carbonates and organic fractions due to the fact that Pb can form stable complexes with Fe and Mn dioxide¹⁶ and may be the reason why reducible Pb is more abundant than the other three non-residual fractions. The association of copper with the different sequential fractions was observed as follows : I – Exchangeable species (5.472%), II – Carbonates (8.927%), III – Fe-Mn oxides (18.265%), IV – Organic fraction (29.098%) and V – Residual fractions (38.238%). For the

Fig. 1. Metals in different fractions in surface soil extracted by the Tessier sequential extraction procedure.

Cu in non-residual fractions, a major portion is bound to the organic matter with comparable amounts associated with the exchangeable fraction, carbonates and Fe-Mn oxide fractions. The fact is that the Cu can easily complex with organic matters because of high formation of organic-Cu compounds¹⁷. From the study it was observed that the copper was mainly bound to organic fraction and this high stability constant of organic-Cu compounds results in stable complex formation between Cu and organic matter¹⁸. Organic matter contents acts an important controlling factors in the abundance of trace metals¹⁹ in the soils or sediments. The major association of Cu with the organic fraction in the studied soils may be due to high formation of organic-Cu complexes. The results indicated that organic matter acted as metal carrier and its complexation with metals played an important role in the distribution patterns of metals in the soil. According to other studies it was also observed that the solubility of Cu is increased under oxidizing conditions, as it is a chalcophile element that is mainly bound to sulfides in nature²⁰. The results agree with the results of other studies^{21,21} which found that a large proportion of Cu in soil is associated with the fraction bound to organic matter.

The association of arsenic with the different sequential fractions was observed as follows : I – Exchangeable species (1.273%), II – Carbonates (4.104%), III – Fe-Mn oxides (15.597%), IV – Organic fraction (31.482%) and V – Residual fractions (47.544%). From the results as shown in Fig. 1, about 50% of the total As in the soils is associated with the non-residual fractions. Though the relatively high concentrations of total arsenic found in all soil samples, this fractionation profile indicates that most of the As found in soil have low mobility because it is mainly bounded to residual fraction (nonlabile) – the most chemically recalcitrant and least bioavailable in soils. Though, under changing environmental conditions they may be released back to the surrounding soil environment by various processes of remobilization. The study revealed that exchangeable and carbonate fractions contains higher % of Cd due to unstable character of these fractions which ultimately may affect the soil ecosystem. Pb, which can form stable complexes with Fe-Mn oxides was predominantly present in the reducible fraction in this study is in agreement with other study²³. Organic fraction contains appreciable amount of As and Cu in this study though these metals may contribute very low toxicity to biota because these fractions are stable in the soil. The percentage of As in the residual fraction suggests that a relatively

high percentage of As in these soils is of lithogeneous origin and cannot be mobilized. It is observed from the results of the fractionation study that the metals in the soils are bound to different fractions with different strengths. The overall percentage of metal content in different fractions is in the sequence of Residual > Organic > Fe-Mn Oxides > Carbonate ≈ Exchangeable and the order of metals in each fractions are presented in Table 3. The metal smelting activities are important sources of potentially toxic elements in the environment, resulting in considerable soil contamination^{24,25}. From the study it was also observed that the metal mining and smelting poses a serious threat to soil contamination by toxic heavy metals.

Mobility factor (MF) :

The mobility of metals in soil profiles may be assessed on the basis of absolute and relative content of fractions weakly bound to the soil components. The mobility factor (MF) which is an index of the bioavailability of metal ions had been proposed³ and applied by several authors^{26,27} to describe heavy metal behavior in soils. The mobility factor can be calculated as follows :

$$\text{Mobility factor (MF)} = \frac{[F_1 + F_2]}{[F_1 + F_2 + F_3 + F_4 + F_5]} \times 100$$

where MF = Mobility factor, F1 = Exchangeable fraction, F2 = Carbonate bound fraction, F3 = Ferrous-manganese bound fraction, F4 = Organic matter bound fraction, F5 = Residual fraction. The result shows that cadmium is potentially mobile and biologically available because of its high MF value. The overall mean results of the present study suggest that the mobility of the metals appeared in the order : Cd (40.627) > Pb (14.941) ≥ Cu (14.399 > As (5.377) suggesting the potential long-term risk of these elements (especially Cd) in the soils. The mobility of metals may be affected by different factors like pH, organic matter content, cation exchange capacity, texture and redox conditions^{28,29}. The high proportion of the chemically reactive forms of Cd is present in the exchangeable and carbonate fractions which is potentially mobile and biologically available also i.e. why MF value is higher for Cd. High MF values are symptoms of relatively high lability and biological availability of heavy metals in soils. The high concentration of metals in the studied soils, and high mobility (high bio-availability) of Cd in the soil indicate potential risk to food-chain via the uptake in plants.

Conclusion

The results of the present investigation based on sequential extraction and speciation analysis revealed that the studied urban soil is significantly contaminated with regard to the huge amounts of Pb, Cd and As. The pH value of the soils in the study area ranged from 6.44 to 7.05 (mean 6.67), indicating an acidic to neutral type of surface soils. The mean concentrations of the Cd, Pb and As in surface soils were higher than the guideline values of China (SEPAC, 1995), but the concentrations of Cu was lower than the limit value. The analytical results indicated that the total concentrations of metals (Cd and Pb) and metalloid (As) were elevated in surface layers for all samples and significant positive correlations among metal pairs could indicate the same or similar source input likely resulting from metal mining and smelting activities. The overall percentage of metal content in different fractions is in the sequence of Residual > Organic > Fe-Mn Oxides > Carbonate > Exchangeable fraction. A significant portion of Pb is bound to the Fe/Mn oxides with comparable amounts associated with the other non-residual fractions and may pose risks under changing environmental conditions. Cd is obviously higher in abundance of the four elements in the exchangeable fraction. Mobility factor indices for soil metals also revealed a high environmental contamination risk for cadmium, which indicate a serious environmental threat.

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